

Research article

Genus *Xanthium* (Asteraceae) in flora of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve (Russia)

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Abstract: The history of *Xanthium* genus research in a protected area in European Russia (Mordovia State Nature Reserve) has been reviewed based on available data (herbarium collections, publications, archive of Chronicles of Nature). We found that *X. strumarium* was the only species, which has been mentioned in the Mordovia State Nature Reserve since 1939. However, the overview of available data allowed us to conclude that all *Xanthium* plants found in this protected area to date belong to *Xanthium orientale*, an invasive alien species.

Keywords: alien species, biodiversity, herbarium, misidentification, protected area

Introduction

Over the last several centuries, many species have been moved from one continent to others (Essl et al., 2020; van Kleunen et al., 2018). Besides the impact to the widely distributed man-influenced ecosystems, the majority of protected areas suffer from alien species impact through the alteration of habitats and the environment, various undesired effects on native species abundance and diversity (Pyšek et al., 2020; Foxcroft et al., 2023; Lysenkov & Galkina, 2023). Inventory of alien plant species and accurate distribution data are necessary to develop the measures for preventing and counteracting alien plant invasion on protected areas (Oswalt et al., 2021).

The genus *Xanthium* L. belongs to subtribe Ambrosiinae (Heliantheae, Asteraceae). It is represented by annual herbaceous plants, which prefer moist sandy pits, river banks, costal dunes, currently expanding to open man-made habitats, like cultivated fields, railway embankments and ruderal sites (Löve & Dansereau, 1959). In the centre of

European Russia, two species of the genus are known, namely *Xanthium orientale* L. (currently often mentioned as *X. albinum* (Widder) Scholz & Sukopp) and *X. strumarium* L. (sometimes mentioned as *Xanthium sibiricum* Patrin ex Widder).

Until late XX century, the most authors did not differentiate these *Xanthium* species. Some authors consider *Xanthium orientale* and *X. strumarium* as synonyms (e.g. Stace, 2019; Magee & Ahles, 2007), while other researchers do not agree with that (e.g. Vinogradova et al., 2010; Tomasello, 2018). Some authors (e.g. Tikhomirov, 1987; Reshetnikova et al., 2010) believe that in the centre of European Russia, *X. strumarium* was replaced by *X. orientale*, a more competitive alien species. This is consistent with data of other studies indicating a decrease in number of *X. strumarium* occurrences, with increase in number of *X. orientale* occurrences, e.g. in Kyrgyzstan (Sennikov & Lazkov, 2021), Lithuania (Gudžinskas, 1997), the Czech Republic (Kaplan et al., 2021), Italy (Müller-Kieffer & Tomasello, 2022), centre of European Russia (Vinogradova et al., 2010). This

Fig. 1. Specimens of *Xanthium* sp. collected in the MSNR (European Russia) and stored in HMNR (left; source [link]) and MW (right; source [link]) herbarium collections.

allows us to suggest that, in Russian herbarium collections, some of *Xanthium* specimens, identified as *X. strumarium*, may actually be *X. orientale*.

This paper was aimed to revise the available information on the genus *Xanthium* in the Mordovia State Nature Reserve (hereinafter – MSNR). For this purpose, we studied the available relevant literature, non-published data, and *Xanthium* spp. specimens, collected in the MSNR.

Material and methods

To investigate the long-term history of the *Xanthium* research in the MSNR, we originally checked the archive of the Chronicles of Nature of the MSNR over 1935–2023. Additionally, we studied the set of the publications on the flora of the MSNR, including three floristic check-lists published until now, namely

Kuznetsov (1960), Borodina et al. (1987), and Vargot et al. (2016).

Herbarium of Mordovia State Nature Reserve (HMNR) and Herbarium of Mordovia State University (GMU) have been checked manually by the authors. The digitised specimens in Herbarium of Lomonosov Moscow State University (MW) have been studied using a web-resource the Moscow Digital Herbarium (Seregin, 2023) (Fig. 1). Third author checked all herbarium specimens of *Xanthium* for the identification correctness.

Results and discussion

In the first check-list of the flora of the MSNR, *X. strumarium* has been indicated (Kuznetsov, 1960), but we are not aware of the herbarium specimens confirming this record. At the same time, we found

the first mentioning of *X. strumarium* in this protected area in the Chronicle of Nature of 1939, which was recently published (Kuznetsov, 2014, p. 189). In the second edition of the flora's check-list of the MSNR (Borodina et al., 1987), the genus *Xanthium* was represented by the taxon named as “*Xanthium rupicola* L.”. It was obviously a mistake because such a taxon has never been described (although we can assume that *X. ripicola* Holub was meant). With this name, this *Xanthium* taxon has been mentioned for the flora of the MSNR until 2016. In the third edition of the flora's check-list (Vargot et al., 2016), this *Xanthium* taxon was spelled as “*Xanthium strumarium* L. [*X. rupicola* L.]”, thus, by saving the previous mistake in a synonym. In the most recent publication on alien flora in the MSNR (Esina et al., 2022), this mistake has been corrected by excluding “*X. rupicola* L.” from the name of this taxon.

The checking of the herbarium collections allowed us to find five specimens originally identified as *Xanthium strumarium* L. Four of them (including three in HMNR and one in GMU) are duplicates found at the sandy spit of a river bank: [USSR, Mordovian Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic], Mordovia State Nature Reserve, quarter 401, sandy spit of the River Moksha, 15.08.1977, L.V. Medvedeva (HMNR, GMU), with approximate coordinates at 54.746° N, 43.075° E. The fifth specimen was found in the MW herbarium: [USSR, Mordovian Autonomous Soviet Socialist Republic], Mordovia State Nature Reserve, quarter 449, side of the road in the Pushta settlement, 20.07.1981, N. Zakhmylova (MW), with approximate co-ordinates at 54.713° N, 43.225° E. However, the revision of all herbarium specimens has allowed us to conclude that all these herbarium specimens are *Xanthium orientale*. Since there are no additional evidences of the presence of other *Xanthium* taxa in the MSNR, we conclude that only *X. orientale* is present in the flora of the protected area.

Thus, taking into account the mentioned above information, we conclude that the wrong name has been used for *Xanthium* plants in the MSNR during 85 years, i.e. from its first mentioning in 1939 (Kuznetsov, 2014, p. 189) until today. For *Xanthium* plants known in the MSNR, we propose using the name *X. orientale*. Of course, we cannot exclude the possible findings of *X. strumarium* in the future as a casual (sensu Richardson et al., 2000; Blackburn et al., 2011) species in the protected area. In addition, we

propose to double-check carefully the identification correctness of *Xanthium* specimens in national, regional and local herbarium collections.

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